

AN EFFECTIVE AND PORTABLE IOT BASED AIR POLLUTION MONITORING SYSTEM

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Abstract:

Air pollution has the potential to harm both current and future generations. Despite numerous government initiatives to restrict this, pollution levels have increased significantly in comparison to the regulations in place. As a regulatory safeguard, a gadget can be used to monitor air pollution in one's home or office, and preventive measures can be taken to reduce pollution on a basic level. For this, we used sensors and a broadcast that sends every update to a mobile device on a time-to-time basis, allowing us to monitor and implement effective pollution-prevention actions. In this paper, we utilized MQ4, MQ9, and DHT22 sensors in conjunction with a Microcontroller Arduino Uno ATmega328p and a GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) module, which allows a mobile device or computer to talk to a wireless network. The time and level of contaminants in the air are displayed on an LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) screen, allowing for monitoring and required preventive steps to be implemented. This proposal contains cost-control measures so that one of these devices can be installed in every home, gated community, or factory to monitor and regulate pollution levels. The levels are presented in real time on both the LCD and the mobile app for easy and effective monitoring.

Keywords: Air pollution, Arduino ATmega328p, MQ4, MQ9, DHT22, GSM module

1. INTRODUCTION

Air is necessary for all the species survival and is a composition of a variety of gases including Nitrogen (N₂), Oxygen (O₂), Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Carbon Monoxide (CO), and a many more rare elements [1]. Human health can be negatively impacted when the natural composition of air is altered. Air pollution is now recognised as the planet's most challenging issues since the development of modern civilization is the one of the most important contributors to climate change. Premature deaths occur all throughout the world. These pollutants had both obstructive and corrosive effects. Human suffering has resulted from economic development. The all-large cities main source of air pollution is due to Vehicles and industries remain the second and third key sources of revenue. Vehicles pollute the environment, which has led in Asthma, lung cancer, Heart strokes and skin cancer and rashes [2, 3]. In recent years, the declining quality of city air has been a global issue of great concern. Air contamination is increasing due to a variety of anthropogenic activities, and is critical in order to minimise and control it. According to a recent study 40% of people in India between the ages of 8 and 14 have subpar lung health. [4, 5]. Several cities in India are considered to be among the most polluted in the world. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), air pollution is directly responsible for millions of

fatalities every year. Additionally, there are no guidelines for reducing death rates provided by the National Air Quality Monitoring Program (NAMP) [6, 7]. Technology in a smart city is used to better the lives of its citizens. Because of this, governments are building smart cities to ensure sustainability and public safety. The proposed system was created by measuring specified contaminants and air factors with High-precision sensors that are available in the market. Air quality, temperature, and humidity can all be monitored with the use of sensors. An Arduino-based microcontroller is used to read and process the data from all of the sensors and then sent the results to the local display.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The effects of air pollution on people and the planet are devastating in large cities. Vehicles and factories are the biggest contributors to air pollution, which in turn contributes to a wide range of respiratory illnesses. Large amounts of carbon dioxide and other dangerous gases emitted by vehicles and businesses contribute to the poor air quality in major cities like Kolkata, Delhi, and Mumbai. Low-cost, portable, and adaptable air pollution detecting systems have been proposed for use in a wide variety of projects [8]. Most modern pollution monitoring systems incorporate the tracking of a wide range of environmental factors. Quite a few studies have achieved significant advancements in this field. Leaks of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), CO₂, and CO can be detected using commercially available metres from manufacturers as Forbix Semicon, Amprobe, Fluke, and many more. Numerous researchers have proposed various systems based on GSM, Geographic Information System (GIS) and Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) technologies for keeping tabs on the state of the air and the decibel count of the noise pollution. However, every technological advancement has restrictions that stem from its primary use [9]. A GIS-based system, for instance, would include a memory buffer, mobile unit, sensors, microcontroller, and internet connectivity via web server to collect information from various locations, including data about time of day and coordinates, so that hotspots of air contamination in specific locations could be monitored [10]. The average of measurements taken in a given area over a certain period of time. The Global Positioning System (GPS) module provides a precise representation of the origin of pollution in any given location. The data is periodically uploaded to a computer via a General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) link. With the user's permission, the collected information is made public on a special webpage [11]. Monika Singh et al. [12] in August 2019 proposed a system to track Air Pollution. The device detects the various atmospheric gases with an Arduino microcontroller linked to a MQ135 and MQ6 gas sensor. When the ppm level rises above a certain threshold, an audible alarm will sound and an internet-connected LCD panel will show the results. Among the many uses they found for these systems were in the monitoring of air quality in industrial perimeter, indoor, reference monitoring station site selection, and data dissemination. Yamunathangam et al. [13] in November 2018 proposed that usage of IoT and cloud will enable real-time, lightning-fast service delivery. Wherever there is severe air pollution, the proposed approach will be implemented. Each potentially harmful pollutant's concentration is tracked regularly. Through the use of an android app, we can calculate the Air Quality Index (AQI) for the detected contaminants and raise public awareness of the issue. Phala et al. [14] in November 2014

presented an Air Quality Monitoring System (AQMS) designed to meet the requirements of the IEEE/IEC 21451 standard. The AQMS gathers data about the air around it through a series of sensors and sends it wirelessly to a central location. A graphical user interface (GUI) was developed to facilitate communication between the system and its intended target. Harsh Gupta et al. [15] in 2019 proposed and developed an IoT based AQMS for Smart Cities. Temperature, humidity, CO, LPG, smoke, and other potentially dangerous air particles can all be measured by smart devices. This information is made available to users all over the world via an Android app. The implications on city dwellers are quantified by accessing and analysing real-time data about air quality via smart devices. In October 2017, Poonam Pal et al. [16] created a device to detect air quality using an Arduino microcontroller with a MQ135 gas sensor to detect the various harmful gases. The voltage readings from the sensor must be transformed into ppm for use. The complete operation was linked to the web via a Wi-Fi module, and the results were displayed on an LCD screen. ‘Fresh Air’ is displayed on the LCD and website when the reading is below 1000ppm, while ‘Poor Air, Open Windows’ is displayed when the value is above the threshold. If it goes up by 2000 ppm, the alarm will sound continuously, and a warning will be shown on the screen and the website ‘Get out into the Open Air.’ Arushi Singh et al. [17] proposed a method of determining both the acoustic environment and the presence of potentially dangerous gases. All forms of pollution, from excessive noise to poisonous gases, are having negative effects on the health of humans and necessitate special attention as pollution levels continue to rise at an alarming rate. Qing Tao et al. [18] suggested a deep learning-based short-term prediction model for PM_{2.5} (particulate matter having an aerodynamic diameter less than or equal to 2.5µm). Temperature, humidity, wind direction, wind speed, and precipitation all have a role in reflecting the dynamics of air pollution. By contrasting the CBGRU model’s predictions with those of standard methods, it is shown that the CBGRU model produces more accurate forecasts at a lower cost.

3. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

Figure 1 shows a block diagram representation Air Pollution Monitoring System based on Arduino Uno. This system is made up of both hardware and software components. Each sensor that is connected to Arduino requires the Arduino IDE software to be programmed.

Figure 1: Block diagram representation of Air Pollution Monitoring System based on Arduino Uno Microcontroller

3.1. Arduino Uno

The ATmega 328p microprocessor serves as the brains of the open-source microcontroller board known as the Arduino Uno, which may be used to build all manner of electronic gadgets. Input/output (I/O) pins on this board can be used to link together a variety of modules, add-on boards, and circuits. The versatility of the Arduino is further enhanced by the inclusion of open-source, computer-based programming tools known as Integrated Development Environment (IDE).

Figure 2: Arduino Uno Board (Front & Back Panel)

It comes with a USB port, a power jack, an ICSP header, a reset button, and 14 digital I/O pins (6 of which can be utilised as PWM outputs). In contrast to its predecessors, the Uno does not rely on the FTDI USB-to-serial driver chip. Instead, it has a USB-to-serial converter-programmed Atmega16U2 (Atmega8U2 up to version R2) [19].

Table 1: ATmega 328p specifications [20]

Specification	Value
Operating Voltage	5 V
Input Voltage	7-12 V (recommended)
DC for I/O pin	40 mA
DC for 3.3V pin	50 mA
Flash Memory	32 KB (0.5KB boot loader)
SRAM	2 KB
EEPROM	1 KB
Clock Speed	16 MHz
Length	68.6 mm
Width	53.4 mm
Weight	25 g

3.2. Sensors

Cost-effective, portable gas sensors are widely used, and five varieties stand out as the best. Unfortunately, there is no single sensor that can detect all of the potentially dangerous substances in the air. Different types of sensors are able to detect different noxious gases. The ideal sensor would be cheap, weigh only a few grammes, and react rapidly (within few seconds). To connect digital information to the real environment, sensors are used [21]. The sensor changes in response to various climate states. The Arduino's input pins are divided into digital and analogue varieties. Moreover, Arduino monitors the sensors for fluctuations, which are then handled in accordance with the code. In our work, the DHT22 measures air temperature and humidity, the MQ-4 detects methane, the MQ-9 detects a potent environmental

toxin CO, and the MG811 calculates CO₂ content in parts per million. All of these sensors are linked together via an Arduino Uno.

DHT22: The DHT22 has only four pins (three of which are utilised) and is a digital temperature and humidity sensor that is cheap and easy to use. In order to measure the relative humidity and temperature of the air, this device uses a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor, and outputs a digital signal via the data pin. You can get away without using analogue input pins [22]. It's simple to navigate and gets fresh content every two seconds. When compared to similar sensors in its class, this one excels in precision and reliability while also offering a wider temperature and humidity operating window.

Figure 3: DHT22 sensor

MQ-4: The MQ-4 sensor is a very accurate methane detector that can be purchased as either a sensor or a module. Within a plastic housing is a small Al₂O₃ ceramic tube, a sensitive tin oxide (SnO₂) layer, a measuring electrode, and a heater. The heater provides the required operating conditions for delicate components. The encased MQ-4 has six pins, four of which are used to gather signals and two of which are used to deliver heating current [23]. Detecting the gas with a MQ sensor is simple. The gas is detected using the analogue pin, and the analogue values (0-5V) are noted with the help of a microcontroller. The concentration of the gas is directly proportional to this value.

MQ-9: To keep tabs on atmospheric CO levels, scientists employ the MQ-9 sensor. It generates an analogue voltage as output. The sensor's CO concentration measurement range is 10 to 10000 ppm. CO, methane, and LPG are all detected with excellent sensitivity by the MQ-9 gas sensor [24]. It uses a cyclic method to detect high and low temperatures (heated by 1.5V). As the concentration of gas increases, so does conductivity of the sensor.

Figure 4: MQ-4 and MQ-9 sensor

3.3. LCD

An electronic display that uses liquid crystals is called an LCD screen. In this research, we used a 16×2 LCD, a common type of display for DIY electronics projects. The two rows of characters on a 16×2 LCD may hold a total of 32. The output of the sensor is shown in Figure 5 for a better understanding of the user.

Figure 5: 16x2 LCD

3.4. GSM Module

Customer applications can take advantage of the SIM900's full Quad-band GSM/GPRS functionality thanks to its SMT module form factor. The SIM900 is small, uses very little power, and supports phone calls, text messages, data transfers, and faxes over the GSM/GPRS 850/900/1800/1900MHz network.

Figure 6: SIM900 GSM Module

3.5. Adapter and Buzzer

High quality, light weight AC-DC adapter for up to 1A loads is used in the hardware, which provides a stable, low ripple, low interference 12V DC output. One type of voice device is the buzzer, which can take an audio model and turn it into an audible signal. It can make a variety of sounds like music, a flute, a buzzer, an alarm, or an electric bell depending on the design and use.

4. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Every sensor action in the system is under the control of the microcontroller, which is its beating heart. The analog pins of the microcontroller with pin numbers a0 and a1 are linked to MQ-9 and MQ-4, respectively. The GSM module, which serves as a communication device, is attached to digital pins 9 and 10, respectively. A dc power adapter provides the GSM module's power source. The ATmega328P microcontroller on which the Arduino Uno is based is an 8-bit device that has proven to be quite successful as the basis for development boards for microcontrollers; it consists of analog and digital pins, reset pins, input/output pins, serial pins, SPI, TWI, AREF, PWM and External interrupts. DHT 22, MQ-4 and MQ-9 sensors are connected to Arduino that DHT 22 positive is connected to 5V and negative is connected to ground and the DHT 22 output pin is connected to Digital pin 2 and this sensor is used to detect the humidity and temperature [25]. MQ 4 V_{CC} is connected to 5V and ground is connected to ground AD pin is connected to analog pin A0 for Arduino, MQ-9 V_{CC} is connected to 5V and ground is connected to ground of Arduino, AD is connected to analog pin A1. This sensor is used in gases like methane, LPG gases etc. Buzzer is connected by the GSM Module and connected to digital pin 9 of Arduino board and LCD display which is used to display the output

that whether the gas is detected or not, the V_{SS} pin is connected to digital ground, V_{CC} and V_{EE} is connected with 5V and ground for digital, RS and ENABLE pins are connected to digital 12 and 11 pins, D4 is to digital pin 5, D5 is to digital pin 4, D6 is to digital pin 3, D7 is to digital pin 6, R/W is to digital ground, LED positive is connected 5V and LED negative is connected to digital ground. Here the gases were detected by using the sensors and GSM module and after the detecting the gas it the buzzer will be alarmed and later the gases are displayed on the LCD display that “gas is detected”. And these gases will be measured in units as ppm. Figure 7 shows a complete hardware connection described so far. The activity can be separated into three sections [5]:

- i. Sensor interfacing with a microcontroller, such as an Arduino.
- ii. Determine gas concentrations under various atmospheric conditions.
- iii. Examining and keeping tabs on data gathered from the screen and serial monitor.

Figure 7: Hardware connections of the complete air pollution monitoring system

To begin, we wired each sensor up to an Arduino to see how it would react. After combining all of the sensors and assigning appropriate codes, we assessed the levels of hazardous substances in different settings.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To ensure the overall functionality of the monitoring system, we tested it both indoors and outdoors. The experimental setup consists of a number of sensors, an Arduino Uno, and a screen. Arduino Uno microcontroller was programmed by connecting to the computer system. The software comes with a serial monitor that can show the readings of all the sensors in the module. We had to test the three distinct types of sensors in our system individually to ensure they all responded as expected. Before testing the DHT22 outside, we measured its response to temperatures in the lab and then watched the LCD and IDE Serial display to see how its readings changed when exposed to sunlight. Since moisture is present in the air coming from mouth, we noticed a change in the sensor’s responsiveness after inhaling the air on DHT22. By burning incense close to the sensor while taking a reading of MQ-9 in the lab under typical conditions (smoke contains CO), we were able to observe a deviation from the expected result; for MQ-4, we kept a gas flame in close proximity to the sensor and recorded the readings, and

then watched how the results shifted again once the adjustments were made. Therefore, we finished our individual sensor testing, and at last, we connected every sensor using an Arduino Uno interface, programmed software to interpret the data. The pollutants are monitored for two days, approximately two hours each day, with the first hour spent taking readings within the laboratory and the second half outside the lab. All of the sensors gave us a consolidated reading, both indoors and out.

Figure 8: Output showing the detection of LPG in the atmosphere

Figure 8 shows the detection of LPG in the atmosphere over time. The analysis of temperature and humidity also aids the weather station in the area's weather predictions. The concentration of diverse aspects aids the pollution control department in defining effective strategies for pollution prevention and control, as well as implementing regulation and enforcement procedures for the next generation.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we set out to develop a simple, low-cost air quality monitoring system based on the Arduino platform. These sensors can be used to gather information in their natural habitat. Pollutants' effects on the climate and human health can be better understood, and localised air pollution can be monitored in real time so that corrective measures can be implemented to maintain a healthy and pollution-free environment. More sensors could be connected to the paper so that the precise amounts of all gases in the air could be measured, and a global positioning system module could be added to track pollution levels. A GSM module can be used to implement this in the future, shrinking the device's footprint so that it can be used in buses and other transport vehicles for long-range interfacing on the power of a battery.

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